

Managed IT Support Services Toronto

Last week our system was completely down. Adi was able to quickly find a technician that was able to service our... office after hours the same day; We were up and running in no time; Rates were reasonable and customer service was excellent. We would highly recommend Synergy IT Solutions Group.[read more](#)

Lorraine Robert 23:28 13 Aug 21

Our go to company for IT & networking services for our clients. Always great & professional service. Swati is very... helpful.[read more](#)

lara alves 19:27 13 Aug 21

Great customer service. Very attentive and professional. I would recommend.

Will Fedel 13:54 09 Aug 21

Great customer service. Professional technician who came to service our plotter. Realized the ordered part was not... necessary. No charge for ordered part. PERFECT! I would recommend this company.[read more](#)

Mladen Kucera 16:59 04 Aug 21

Working with Synergy for almost 3 years. Very professional stuff. Mostly, I worked with Adi and Chirag. Great guys.... Responsive and knowledgeable. They have always right advice for your solution. Wish them the best [read more](#)

Ishan Gadkari 16:36 09 Jul 21

Synergy IT solutions would be my first choice while having any printer issues. We've had countless issues with printers... in our facility and every time we've received quality service from this organization. They're very responsive and have solutions to all the issues.[read more](#)

Dundas University Health [it support for logistics lauderdale](#) Clinic 18:50 08 Jul 21

Dharmveer is our IT guy! he is prompt with his reply and gets things done same day. The team here has been amazing. Surpassed any expectations. Their troubleshooting skills and layers of knowledge... are deep. We have successfully completed our project thanks to Synergy, Adi and the Team of great techs. I will use them again and again with any clients that have IT needs beyond my skills which without consistent education are diminishing with time. take care, and thanks again.[read more](#)

UTIL Hostmonitor 22:44 25 Feb 21

Great response! I had great experience with Synergy team, Their response is swift and so are their actions. We're glad... we chose SynergyIT, looking forward to work together for upcoming projects.[read more](#)

I Rafiq 17:54 23 Feb 21

On behalf of mijava Corporation of Canada. Thank you Synergy IT for the great support & service has extended to... mijava! Thank you Bhavin and Adi for the Trusted Advisory Approach! Incredibly helpful in these tough economic challenges! Amazing to work with and would recommend them to any firm who will need the best

services and support! Thank you again Adi and Bhavin! Imran. read more

Andrew Ying 17:19 17 Feb 21

I've been working with Synergy IT Solution for the past 5 years. Their teams are professional, knowledgeable and Adi... is a great person to work with. When they came to me for any security advice they were open to all my suggestions. I worked under their specific guidelines which was nice to see they had given this much thought. They are fast in the decision making. A pleasure to work with. I highly recommend Synergy IT Solution. read more

tait rene 17:01 22 Oct 20

Company was extremely patient with me. Great help was provided to reset system. I thought I called google (I am 65 yo)... We have bought all our computer equipment from Synergy. Their earlier companies for 30 years. Reliable. Try hard....